

The need for open country-tailored sector coupled Energy System Models and an Approach for Austria

Max NUTZ¹, Isabelle GRABNER¹, Florian SCHEIBER¹, Vartan AWETISJAN², Helmut WERNHART², Nicole ZECHNER², Philip WORSCHISCHEK², Johannes SCHMIDT¹

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Motivation: Climate Crisis

- **Rapid and Just transformation to Carbon Neutral Societies**
- Paris Agreement 2015 → NTCs

→ Decarbonization of Energy Sector

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Motivation: Energy Security

- **Reliance on few regimes/states**

Energy at heart of transition

- **Renewable Energies are key for decarbonization**
- Economic relevance – capital intensive
- Social relevance – regional impacts

→ Careful and transparent planning

Energy System modelling

- Geographical interconnection
- Sectoral interconnection

- Fully sector coupled
- Minimization of investment and operational costs
- Emission constraints

National energy system planning need for detail

- **Multi-regional scale**
 - Technology roadmaps
 - renewable carrier usage
 - International collaboration

Multi-regional ESM

National energy system planning need for detail

- **Multi-regional scale**
 - Technology roadmaps
 - renewable carrier usage
 - International collaboration
- **(Sub-) national scale**
 - Infrastructure needs
 - Generation regionalization

Multi-regional ESM

National ESM

Wind availability - 2013-11-01 00:00

Wind availability - 2013-11-01 00:00

Highlighted regions

Highlighted regions

International optimization national sovereignty

Wind electricity production in Austria

Ignoring national sovereignty

→ Non-realistic optimization results

Nationally tailored Energy System Models

→ Preserving national planning context ...

spatial
resolution

national policies

national data
and studies

regional
characteristics

National Energy System Modelling in international context

Nationally tailored Energy System Models

→ Preserving national planning context ...

spatial
resolution

national policies

national data
and studies

regional
characteristics

National Energy System Modelling in international context

Dynamic international
network and flows

Model validation on
respective country

international policy
goals

... while enabling international coordination

PyPSA-AT nationally tailored ESM for Austria

[https://github.com/
aggm-ag/pypsa-at](https://github.com/aggm-ag/pypsa-at)

- Open source and open data
- Nationally tailored to Austria

PyPSA-AT nationally tailored ESM for Austria

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PyPSA-AT nationally tailored ESM for Austria

- Open source and open data
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- brownfield-data
- policy goals (constraints)
- local potential studies
- infrastructure specifics

Open source: PyPSA-Ecosystem

Open

Open data

PyPSA-Earth

PyPSA-AT nationally tailored ESM for Austria

- Model Validation: Eurostat Energy Balance

PyPSA-AT model validation (validation year 2020)

PyPSA-AT validation against IAMC Energy Balance

Use case: infrastructure requirements in AT

- Net-zero system
- Transmission grid
- Pipelines
- technologies

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*Common scenario assumptions
[Final demand drivers, exogenous technological choices (e.g. steel production technology), import limits, policies]*

Use case: full climate neutrality in Austria

- Net-zero system
- Transmission grid
- Pipelines
- technologies

Sum up to take away

- **International Context** highly relevant in (national) energy system planning
- **Nationally tailored Energy System Models**
- **PyPSA-AT** - nationally tailored ESM for Austria

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Thank you!

LinkedIn

www.linkedin.com/company/cross-sec-2040/
<https://www.linkedin.com/in/max-nutz/>

Bluesky

bsky.app/profile/cross-sec.bsky.social
<https://bsky.app/profile/maxnutz.bsky.social>

www.netzero2040.at/cross-sec
<https://github.com/maxnutz> | max.nutz@boku.ac.at

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